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The Evolution and Decline of Indigenous Education: A Historical Analysis

Dr. Aribam Pratima Devi

Former Research Associate, Center of Research, Indian Institute of Teacher Education, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India.

Dr. Sudhir Kumar Tandel

Associate Professor, Indian Institute of Teacher Education, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India.

Prof. Jayna Joshi

Professor, Indian Institute of Teacher Education, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India.

Dr. Bhavesh Raval

Associate Professor, Indian Institute of Teacher Education, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India.

Abstract:

Indigenous education was the sole reservoir and disseminator of various types of education throughout India. The community mostly funded these schools, which were established in religious or public places. These schools educated children aged six to fourteen, teaching them basic skills such as reading, writing, and arithmetic. This article focuses on the indigenous education system, with a special emphasis on primary schools in Gujarat. It explores the origins of this system, which began in private homes and religious institutions and discusses teaching methods, student demographics, and teacher qualifications and remuneration. The article also provides a statistical review of indigenous schools in the Bombay State, from 1823 to 1936. Furthermore, it examines how this education system began to disappear during the British administration.

Introduction

The indigenous education system in the state of Gujarat which was then part of the Bombay state began informally in open spaces, and private homes which slowly evolved into more formal institutions of private and state-funded education. Before the British introduced western education system in the 19th century, indigenous education was the main source of

knowledge dissemination in India. These schools were funded by the local community and usually located in religious or public places. They taught children aged 6 to 14 with the basic skills of reading, writing, and arithmetic.

Most of the students in these schools came from Brahmin or business families. Children from lower castes, such as *Antyajias*, were not allowed to attend. The majority of the teachers were Brahmins, but there were also some teachers from *Vania*, *Kanbi*, and *Brahmkshatriya* communities. For Brahmins, teaching was often a family tradition, passed down from one generation to the next.

The teachers were paid in both cash and kind (Government of Gujarat, 1980, p. 329). This institution had a symbiotic connection with the dominant social order, having evolved and survived until the beginning of the 20th century. It also had a significant impact on the formation of British education policy in India, as the latter was built on the foundation laid by the former (Radhakrishnan, 1990).

Indigenous Education

The modern education system in India was formed during British rule, at the expense of traditional indigenous education. The term indigenous education refers to a system of education that developed within a country, which is deeply rooted in its culture, and is free of external influences. It includes traditional methodologies, philosophical teachings, and practices that have been passed down through generations (Sarkar & Debsarma, 2021).

Native schools were the primary source of indigenous education. The Education Commission of 1882 identified these institutions as those operated by Indians using traditional techniques. Examples included *tols* (Sanskrit learning centres), *maktabs* and *madradas* (Muslim schools and colleges), and village schools, which taught the children of tradesmen, small landowners, and wealthy farmers (Government of India, 1883, p.56). Prior to colonisation, indigenous education was divided into two categories: primary and higher education. *Pathshalas* and *maktabs* offered primary education, whereas *tols* and *madradas* offered higher education. The social, cultural, political, economic, institutional, and educational methods of these institutions were very different.

Nature of Indigenous Education

In 1824-25, Mountstuart Elphinstone, the governor of Bombay at that time, issued a report on indigenous education in the province. According to the report, there was no proper school building dedicated to Indigenous education and it was disseminated in private houses, temples, mosques, sheds, or houses of teachers. There was no consistency in the schools, and schooling began and ended according to local demands (Naik & Nurullah, 1974, p.10). In Ahmedabad, the largest number of students in a school was 102, with an average of 64 students.

In Surat, the average number of students per school was 53 (Parulekar, 1951, p.xxii). Schooling was open to all who could afford it, except females and low castes and it was thus dominated by Brahmins, who made up the majority of teachers and 30% of students (Naik & Nurullah, 1974, p. 10).

Schools:

The common schools at that time were one-teacher schools. However, in Gujarat, an assistant was hired by the teacher who was either a relative of the teacher, where schools were often large. The assistant was sometimes a head student who was sometimes absolved from paying his dues to the school for the service (Parulekar, 1951, p.xxii). The schoolmasters occasionally used the cane liberally as a disciplinary method. Students at these institutions were often from a variety of social classes, including children of laborers (coolees) and Rajputs. However, no children from the Dhooria community were sent to school.

Students:

Around 30% of Hindu students in the schools were Brahmins, though this ratio varied by district, with Ahmedabad having only 15%. Brahmins had more access to education than other Hindu groups, while accounting for only around 5% of the Hindu population. Other castes, such as the *Wanis* (Baniyas or Vaishyas), *Sonars* (goldsmiths), and *Prabhoos* (zamindars), had a large number of students in schools during that time. The actual age of the students is unspecified. However, there is mention of young children frequently taken to school not to learn, but to keep them out of mischief (Parulekar, 1951, p.xxx).

Course of Instruction:

In the Gujarati schools, arithmetic was taught with a strong focus on account management and simple interest. Learning multiplication tables was given much importance along with reading and writing letters. First, the students were made to memorise numbers from 1 to 100 followed by learning multiplication tables and addition. After the numbers were learned, the teachers made them learn the alphabet, reading and writing, measurement, time, and money. Moral values and religious principles were also taught to the students in these schools. Learning multiplication tables was seen as a foundation for banias or traders as it would later help them in their business. These tables were memorised in schools by recitation in small groups. Reading and writing skills were made to learn at home or in shops.

Remuneration of Teachers:

The remuneration of teachers varied in different places of Gujarat. In some districts, there was no payment of monthly salary or cash. Rather, the students gave gifts to the teachers on a daily basis that compensated the monthly salary of the teachers. Although, cash was paid to the teachers on various dates, such as starting of school, completion of instruction, and at the time of leaving school. The remuneration paid was not fixed and it depended on the abilities of

the parents of the students. However, a system was developed in these schools to not compensate the monthly salary with gifts when there were fifty or more students. Each student offered two grain seers and the weight of four copper *plee* ghee which remained constant regardless of the number of students on every fiftieth day alternately.

In the town of Jamboosar, an amount ranging from rupees 6 to 21 per month was paid yearly. In Kaira district, students frequently approach the guests of high status who stop by the villages and beg things for their teachers. In the Ahmedabad and Surat districts, there is mention of land given to teachers for their service. The salaries of teachers differed in Surat. A village teacher with a class strength of fifty students earned approximately rupees 3 per month, while a teacher in the city, earned around rupees 5 per month. A school teacher in the Broach district earned around rupees 20 to 50 annually, depending on the size of the village. The annual salary of teachers rarely exceeded rupees 150 even in large schools with 100 or more students. There is mention of the hiring of an assistant teacher by the teachers themselves and their salary was paid from their own in such schools (Parulekar, 1951, p. xxiv).

Qualifications of Teachers:

There were no fixed criteria for becoming a teacher in the indigenous schools. The basic qualifications for a school teacher were good handwriting and the ability to read simple texts. It was often found that the teachers were uneducated and lacked adequate educational qualifications. They were supposed to teach the fundamentals of the three R's and were expected to have a solid grasp of multiplication and other complex tables. Most of the school teachers, although were not well educated but were qualified enough to impart the relatively limited fare of schooling for which the students came to their schools (Parulekar, 1951, p.xxvii).

Student-teacher Relationship:

The student teacher relationship in the indigenous schools was very good. The school teachers were paid much respect and regard by their students. The students often bow to their teachers as a way of showing respect. The *Puntojee* or *Meheta* (school teacher) was seen as a person of importance and respect within the community despite their poor economic status. The teachers were respected by the parents of the students as well as the society. The students showed their love and respect for their teachers in various ways (Parulekar, 1951, p. xxx).

Indigenous Elementary Schools from 1883-1936 in the Bombay State

The state of Gujarat was founded in 1960, before which it was part of the Bombay state. The following section presents insights into the history of indigenous elementary schools before the foundation of Gujarat State. Various documents such as a review of education in Bombay state 1855-1955 issued by the Department of Education, Bombay 1958, Gazetteers of Bombay State and Gujarat, and the Gujarat- A reference annual series were referred to for this section.

A review of education in Bombay state 1855-1995 published by the Department of Education, Bombay 1958 reveals that there was a good number of indigenous schools that coexisted with the modern schools in the early nineteenth century.

Table 1: Indigenous Elementary Schools from 1823-1936

Year	Number of Schools	Number of Students
1823	1500	31,000
1828	1680	33,000
1842	1420	30,000
1847	1751	33,265
1855	2386	70,314
1863	2921	77,137
1875	3330	78,952
1882	3954	78,205
1891	2487	58,608
1901	2470	63,196
1921	1139	29,501
1936	542	25,017

Source: A Review of Education in Bombay State 1855-1995, p. 70

Table 1 reveals that the number of indigenous schools increased between 1823 and 1882. There was a rapid expansion of these schools during these years. In the year 1823, there were 1500 schools with 31,000 students. By 1882, the number of schools increased to 3954. The number of students increased from 1823 to 1875 with a drop in number in the year 1842. After 1875 the number of students decreased. While the number of schools and students increased steadily from 1847 to 1875, the number of students declined after that. In 1882, the number of schools reached a peak with a number of 3954 schools, there was a noticeable decline by 1891. This declining trend continued into the early 20th century. By 1921, the number of schools had drastically decreased to 1139 with only 29,501 students, and by 1936, it decreased further to only 542 schools with 25,017 students.

Decline of Indigenous Elementary Schools

There was an expansion of Indigenous schools from 1823 to 1882 after which a decline was seen as indicated in Table 1. The decline in these schools could be because of many reasons. The major reason could be the lack of support extended by the British officers at that period as they believed that these schools were of no value. However, some British officers supported and encouraged these indigenous schools. The then governor of Bombay from 1819 to 1827, Elphinstone wanted to develop the Indigenous schools into a national educational system, but the administrators did not agree to that. Moreover, the Board of Education and the Bombay Native Education Society did not attempt to support or expand indigenous schools. As a result, no grant was given to any indigenous schools until 1870.

Another reason for the decline could be the expansion of departmental schools. After 1882, the number of indigenous schools was decreasing and the school teachers were rapidly becoming extinct, with departmental school graduates filling the majority of their posts. Additionally, the inclusion of indigenous elementary schools on the grant-in-aid list, which was a growing public preference for Local Board Schools, and the replacement of the old school teacher (Government of Bombay, 1958) could be another reason for the decline of indigenous education which was observed in the late nineteenth and the early twentieth century. The number of schools dropped from 2470 in 1901, to 1139 in 1921 to only 542 in 1936.

The impact of British policies had a significant role to play in the decline of the Indigenous schools. The lack of funding and official recognition of these schools further accelerated the disappearance of these schools. Furthermore, the introduction of English education that produced an elite class also led to the decline of Indigenous schools. An additional reason for the decline could be the fact that the indigenous education system was no longer relevant in the twentieth century. Indigenous education was deeply rooted and taught in vernacular languages, which was unable to keep up with the rapidly changing social landscape of that time. The indigenous primary schools might have remained traditional because they could not change or adapt according to the needs of the society which furthermore contributed to its decline.

Another reason for the decline of indigenous education could be the introduction of English education which was regarded as more progressive and modern. Moreover, English

education did not discriminate the students on the basis of caste and fulfilled the needs of the modern society at that point in time which made it more preferable and a better choice of education than the indigenous way of learning. The indigenous education was denied to the students of lower caste and discriminatory.

:Conclusion

The indigenous system of education had a glorious past before the influence of English education. This system of education was independent and was organised as a hierarchical network of pathshalas, tols, maktabas, and madrasas. It was focused more on the arithmetic and basic reading and writing skills. The teachers were treated with utmost respect in spite of their poor economic status. This education system was supported by some British officials while some officials considered it outdated and of no value. There is still an ongoing debate on the characteristics and significance of indigenous education as it is underrepresented in many documents. However, the decline of this education system is evident from the number of schools and students enrolled. This decline could be because of various reasons, majorly from the ignorance of the British officials and the introduction of English education. The indigenous education could not adapt to the rapidly changing landscape of the modern society and slowly led to its complete vanish.

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